

SOCIO-POLITICAL CONTENT AND CONSEQUENCES OF POVERTY

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Abstract. The article considers the concept of poverty, its essence, causes and various socio-political views, measurements and approaches to determining its criteria as the main problem. The main methods for determining the poverty standard and threshold, the analysis of statistical data on determining the standard of living of the population, improving health, longevity, literacy indicators and achieving an increase in living standards are presented, and scientific conclusions and recommendations are given on the socio-political significance of poverty.

Keywords: poverty, institutional poverty, regional poverty, class poverty, absolute and relative poverty, macropoverty, micropoverty.

INTRODUCTION. Poverty has become one of the most acute socio-economic problems in the world in the context of today's globalization. Political parties, governments and all strata of society in different countries have always attached great importance to the issue of poverty, for this purpose we need to clarify the concept of poverty.

The concept of poverty has a meaning in accordance with its established criteria. At the same time, poverty is determined on the basis of various criteria and measurements worldwide. Therefore, understanding and studying the concept of poverty can lead to the formation of colorful ideas. That is, it is of urgent importance to comprehensively clarify the concept of poverty and to have clear knowledge and skills about its essence, types and manifestations.

Historically, understanding the problem of poverty has been a unique approach to finding a solution to it. The Chinese philosopher and founder of Taoism, Lao Tzu, once said, "Give a hungry man a fish and he will eat for a day. Give him a fishing rod and teach him how to fish and he will eat for a lifetime." [1]

Our great thinker, the sultan of poetic property, statesman A. Navoiy in his work Mahbub ul-Ulub thinks about this as follows:

"It is a pain to take a dime,

It is better if someone gives a fortune" [2]

Understanding poverty as a problem has become one of the global issues of our century. The Minister of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Jamshid Kuchkarov, said in one of his reports, "No one used the word poverty in our country until now. I can say from my long-term work in the field of economics that we once developed a program called "Increasing the well-being of the population", as if we did not have poor people" [3], which today requires a deep study of poverty in its true sense.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. According to the concepts and opinions of our country's scientists on the issue of poverty, O.Kh. Makhmudov defined poverty as a characteristic of the economic status of a person or social group who cannot meet the minimum needs that are important for life, are unable to work, and cannot continue to do the work they want [4] and determined the criterion of poverty based on the lack of sufficient opportunities for a person, while Sh.I. Mustafaulov, N. Murodullayev, R. Khamidov, O. Rahimberdiyev, "Poverty is an indicator of the economic status of a person or social group who cannot meet the minimum needs necessary for survival, maintaining their ability to work, and continuing the continuity of generations. Poverty is a relative concept and depends on the general standard of living in each society. The state of poverty "indicates that there is no possibility of compensating for the long-

term shortage of resources either with previous savings or with funds accumulated through temporary savings from the purchase of expensive goods" [5].

Researchers from Russia and other CIS countries, such as N. Arkhangelskaya, [6] L. Akhmadeyev, [7] A. Bachurin, [8] S. Belozerova, [9] L. Bondarenko, [10] Y. V. Burlakova, [11] N. D. Vavilina, [12] S. A. Varvus, [13] N. Ivanov and N. Goffe [14], have shed more light on issues related to poverty and have defined the poor as a population group that does not have the economic capacity to solve existing problems in social life.

Prominent foreign economists such as D. Hobson, [15] D. Sachs, [16] G. E. Slezingler, [17] Z. Williams, [18] F. Williams, [19] R. Hivman [20] have further enriched scientific theories on the study of poverty and other social problems of the population.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Poverty can be divided into different types from different perspectives or according to different standards. First of all, according to the meaning of poverty, it can be divided into poverty in the broad sense and poverty in the narrow sense.

Poverty in the narrow sense means the inability to satisfy the most basic needs of life under a certain mode of social production and threatens the continuation of life. This is mainly in the sense of satisfying the physiological needs of people. The lack of a minimum standard of living to ensure physiological needs is poverty.

Poverty in the broad sense includes not only the inability to satisfy the most basic needs for survival, but also social, cultural, environmental and other factors, such as cultural and educational conditions, medical and health conditions, living environment conditions and life expectancy of the population. Poverty in the broad sense is a much broader concept than poverty in the narrow sense. The World Bank's World Development Report 2000/2001 provides a broad definition of poverty. The report notes that, in addition to material deprivation, low levels of education and health, poverty also includes vulnerability to hazards and risks, as well as the inability to express one's needs and lack of influence.

According to the causes of poverty, it can be divided into general poverty, institutional poverty, regional poverty and class poverty. General poverty is poverty that arises from a low level of economic and social development. For example, in primitive society, due to the low level of productivity, underdeveloped production activities, and very little food, primitive people actually lived in conditions of widespread poverty.

Institutional poverty is associated with the unequal distribution of living resources among different communities, regions, social groups and individuals, determined by socio-economic, political and cultural systems, leading to the fact that certain communities, regions, social groups and individuals are in a state of poverty.

Regional poverty is a phenomenon of poverty caused by difficult natural conditions and a low level of social development. The poor distribution of the rural population of my country has clear regional characteristics and is concentrated in a number of regions with relatively difficult natural conditions.

Class poverty is understood as poverty caused by the physical fitness of certain individuals, families or social groups, low level of education, lack of labor resources in the family, lack of means of production and social relations.

Poverty is both an absolute and a relative concept, so poverty can be divided into absolute poverty and relative poverty. Absolute poverty, also known as subsistence poverty, is the lack of the minimum necessities of life and the inability to support the most basic needs of life.

Relative poverty is also known as relative poverty. This means that although the problem of food and clothing has been solved, there may be significant income differences between different social members and different regions. Low-income individuals, families and regions are relatively poor.

In order to correctly understand the real living conditions of the poor and to provide a scientific basis for formulating anti-poverty strategies and policy measures, the level of poverty, that is, the poverty line, must be scientifically determined. Individuals or families whose standard of living is below the poverty line are poor and in need of social support and assistance. The poverty line defined by the World Bank is an annual per capita consumption expenditure of US\$270-370, calculated on the basis of constant 1985 purchasing power parity prices. Experts from the International Labour Organization suggest that the poverty line in industrialized countries should be approximately 30% of the average wage of production workers, while the Economic Commission for Europe recommends that the poverty line be 50% of a single wage for adults.

Currently, there are four main methods for determining the poverty line internationally. One of them is the International Poverty Standards Act. This is the income-proportionate method proposed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. That is, 50 to 60% of the income or average income of residents of a country or region is used as the poverty line of that country or region, which is the minimum living security limit. The second is the subsistence needs method, also known as the "market basket method". To determine the poverty line using this method, we first need to list the goods and services needed to ensure the minimum standard of living in the local area, including the types and quantities of goods and services, and then calculate the number of people who own these goods and services based on market prices. How much cash is needed and the amount of cash is the poverty line. The third is the lifestyle method. It first starts from people's lifestyles, consumption behaviors and other "lifestyles" and raises a series of questions about family life patterns, and then selects a series of deprivation indicators, that is, the abandonment of a certain lifestyle and consumption behaviors in a certain life. form, then based on these deprivation indicators and the actual living conditions of the respondents, determine who is poor, and then analyze their deprivation needs, consumption and income to calculate the poverty line. The fourth is the Engel coefficient method, which divides the absolute expenditure of the family on food consumption by a certain Engel coefficient to find the necessary consumption expenditure, that is, the poverty line. This is also the income ratio method derived from the "Engel law". The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations defines poverty as an Engel coefficient of 60%. The consumption expenditure calculated using this data is the poverty line, which is the minimum security for living. In the United States, if 1/3 of a family's expenses are spent on food, it is considered a poor family or poor, and therefore requires social assistance. The "poverty line" in the United States is three times the minimum income standard for food expenses.

Any family or individual with an income equal to or below this level is eligible for social assistance. Currently, most countries use the share of food expenditures as a basis for measuring family wealth and implementing social assistance.

It is very important to address the problem of poverty. Poverty is actually hierarchical, and it is necessary to distinguish between "macropoverty" and "micropoverty".

The first is poverty in the regional sense, that is, macropoverty, which looks at poverty from a general perspective. For example, national poverty, regional poverty, rural poverty, urban poverty, etc. If understood from this perspective, not all low-income countries are poor countries, and not all high-income countries are poor countries. This type of poverty problem is also called underdevelopment, which is the subject of development economics research;

The second is individual poverty, which is the view of poverty from the perspective of individuals and families. From this perspective, poverty exists in all countries. For example, in 2004, the poverty rate in the United States was 12.7%, meaning one in eight people were poor. In this sense, poverty can be considered a persistent problem if the distribution of income and

wealth is not completely equal. If these two concepts of poverty are combined, this has a significant negative impact.

According to the explanation of “Merryman, Websters Dictionary”, “poverty” is a state in which a person does not have the usual or socially acceptable amount of money or material wealth. Individuals, families, and groups who do not have the resources to obtain a variety of food products, participate in social activities, and meet the minimum living and social conditions are called poor.”

The concept of poverty continues to deepen, and the perspectives on studying poverty are constantly changing. No matter how poverty is defined, it is very difficult to give a comprehensive and scientific definition. Perhaps that is why the World Bank prefers a descriptive explanation of the concept of poverty. Poverty is a state of existence that people want to avoid. Poverty means hunger and lack of a place to live. Poverty means hunger, lack of clothing and medicine, lack of access to school and lack of education. Poverty means unemployment, fear of looking to the future and a constant threat to life. Poverty means that children get sick or even die because of their uncleanliness. Poverty means the loss of power and freedom.

CONCLUSION. Based on the above considerations, understanding the concept of poverty and its broader meaning determines recommendations and conclusions of socio-political importance. In particular,

- is based on the inclusion of social indicators in determining the overall assessment of living standards;

- relies on measures of health, longevity and literacy;

- is measured as the proportion of the population with access to health care;

- is provided with safe drinking water;

- is measured as the number of children under 5-10 years of age who are malnourished.

Two aspects seem to be particularly important in assessing poverty for each country.

The first concerns the risk and volatility of income, which often manifests itself in a sense of vulnerability. In describing how market fluctuations, seasons and crises affect their well-being, the poor provide an understanding of poverty not only as a state of having nothing, but also as the easy loss of what one has. “Vulnerability” has two dimensions: the external side of shocks, stress, and risk, and the internal side of isolation and helplessness. On both sides, the means to overcome devastating losses are almost nonexistent or imperfect.

The second is the lack of voice and political rights. The lack of voice and political rights is often described as a feeling of powerlessness. They are disadvantaged in terms of both resources and rights, and are unable to be heard by others. As an economically marginalized group, they are also easily marginalized socially and suffer from a degree of social exclusion. In terms of efficiency and distributive justice, they lack trust, relationships, interpersonal connections, cooperation, and coordination.

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